

Enhancing Equity and Access to Stem Education through Virtual Field Trips: A Systematic Review

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This study systematically reviewed and analyzed previous studies that investigate the effects of virtual field trips and those that compare their effects to other instructional strategies on STEM learning outcomes. Peer-reviewed papers were searched using a variety of databases, including Google, Google Scholar, Academia, Research Gate, Ask the public, conferences, journals, online library, and electronic journals. Using a protocol as the basis of inclusion and exclusion. Any research article that investigates the effects of virtual field trips or compares its effect to other instruction on any of the students' learning outcome variables (achievement, performance, retention, attitude, motivation, practical skills and interest) is considered. The inclusion criteria are that: only articles from 2012-2024 that examine the effect of virtual field trips and any of the variables. Therefore, any article before 2012 or did not study at least one of the variables was excluded. A total of 15 articles were selected and used for this study. The result of the review reveals a positive association between virtual field trips and various STEM learning outcomes, particularly students' interest. Also Consistent findings indicate that virtual field trips may improve student achievement, performance, motivation, enhance access to practical learning skills, and more positive attitudes towards STEM. The review concludes that future research should prioritize investigating the effect of virtual field trips with diverse educational settings, particularly primary and secondary schools. Studies should examine the impact of virtual field trips on knowledge retention.

Keywords
Virtual Field Trips, STEM Education, Equity, Access, learning Outcomes.

Introduction

Technological developments and globalization are changing every aspect of life. In today's science and technology era, there is a great need to improve the quality of education, especially in science education. This can be achieved by bringing fundamental changes through ICT-driven innovative teaching and learning strategies that can provide student-centered learning environments that make learning processes more interesting to students (Tafa et al, 2020). The rapid spread of technology in schools has revolutionized teaching and learning, transforming the interaction of teachers, students, curricula, and learning resources. (Uğur et al, 2019). In STEM fields, technology empowers students to engage in dangerous, and complex experiments that would otherwise be inaccessible, overcoming limitations posed by cost, safety, and logistical constraints (Akçayır et al., 2016). However, in places affected by conflict or disasters, students

often lack access to high-quality STEM education. Virtual field trips offer a promising alternative for addressing these challenges by providing all students with equitable access to engaging and immersive learning environments, without compromising their safety.

Virtual Field Trips (VFTs) are one of the types of technology that has been integrated into the classroom. It is a guided exploration through the World Wide Web that organizes a collection of pre-screened, thematically based web pages into a structured online learning experience. (Foley, 2017). According to Khotima et al (2021), Virtual field trip (VFT) is a collection of technology-based resources used together to give students the learning experiences gained from an actual field trip. Newsome (2013) defined Virtual Field Trip as a live interactive program taught by a content provider to a classroom through the use of video conferencing technology. However, Lawal (2023), believes that VTFs are used both as a supplement to field

trips as well as to provide an alternative when an actual field trip experience is not possible. Similarly, Spicer and stratford in Zakareeya (2019), reported that VFTs can be an alternative or complementary to field activities because they are able to simulate the realities of the “outside” world in the classroom.

Opalewski and O’Leary, (2019) found that many cultural institutions utilize technology to provide distance learning opportunities or virtual field trips for students. When used effectively, technology can open students to new experiences and places and many of the obstacles that teachers face with a traditional field trip no longer apply. Zanetis (2010) asserts that teachers do not need to worry about money, getting permission, scheduling chaperones, taking medical risks, or skipping out on important classroom instruction time. Thus when traditional field trips are not possible, virtual field trips offer a viable alternative. Technology empowers educators to offer novel learning experiences, facilitating connections with diverse individuals and locations through tools like videoconferencing and internet resources. The potential advantages of virtual environments, particularly in Biology education, are substantial in today's digital age. As technological tools such as educational games, online simulations, and virtual learning environments become increasingly prevalent, there's a growing need for educational researchers to deeply investigate their impact on learning outcomes (Mahya, 2017).

Several researches were conducted on the effects of virtual field trips in education including reviews, scoping and systematic reviews. Some of such work include that of Raheem and Adekunle (2024) on the effect of virtual field trips on secondary school students’ cognitive proficiency in biology: a systematic review; Sharafadeen and Adekunle (2024) A systematic review on the impact of virtual field trips on secondary school students’ cognitive competence in biology; and that of Anilas ana Janetta (2021) A scoping review on the effects

of virtual reality on student learning. These reviews channel effort toward examining the effects of virtual field trips in promoting student learning outcomes. Despite the effort put by previous systematics reviews, intensive review of the existing literature revealed no systematic review was carried out specifically on effects of virtual field trips in enhancing equity and access to STEM education in Nigerian secondary schools. Also the reviews conducted by previous reviewers did not involve major parameter that shows methodology and the actual processes the researchers follow in their empirical researches.

Recent studies, such as those by Lawal (2023); Haris and Osman (2015); Amna (2023); Emrah and Recap (2023); Dongyang et al, (2023) have highlighted the potential of VFTs to overcome logistical and safety concerns in STEM education. However, gaps remain in understanding the specific learning outcomes affected by VFTs across different STEM fields and educational levels. This study aims to bridge these gaps by systematically reviewing recent literature on the subject. Therefore, this systematic review aims to retrieve empirical studies investigating the effect of virtual field trips on STEM learning outcomes, including those that compare the effects of virtual field trips to other instructional strategies with reference to STEM Education, covering a period of 13 years (2012-2024) to enable the researcher to include all accessible and relevant articles published in impact factor journals. It will also enable the researcher to present a comprehensive outlook on literature and state of the art on field trips and STEM learning. In specific terms, the review address the following issues: Distribution of research on the effect of virtual field trips in STEM by country, publication type, STEM field, and educational level, the research design and instruments used by researchers in assessing the effect of virtual field trip on students learning outcomes in STEM education, the learning outcomes examined by researchers in assessing the effect

of virtual field trips in STEM education and the key findings on the effect of virtual field trips on student learning outcomes in STEM education.

Methodology

A systematic review is a scholarly synthesis of evidence on a clearly presented topic using critical methods to identify, select, define, organize, synthesize, and assess previous research on variables intended to study. This review was based on five stages: search strategy, inclusion and exclusion criteria, framework analysis, and quality assessment, adapted from PRISMA. The review searched relevant literature using the keywords virtual field trips and STEM education and equity. The review searched relevant literature using keywords “virtual field trips and STEM, education and access,” “virtual field trips, STEM education” and socioeconomic status, ““virtual field trips, STEM education” and achievement,” “virtual field trips, STEM education” and interest, ““virtual field trips, STEM education and motivation,” “virtual field trips, STEM education” and retention, ““virtual field trips, STEM education” and practical knowledge skills,” “virtual field trips, STEM education” and performance, ““virtual field trips, STEM education” and equity. The search engine and database used included goggles, goggle scholars, research gates, the public, IEEE, E-library, journals, conferences, and electronic journals. The results were obtained from 47 articles. These were selected to ensure all relevant publications were identified. It also allow the researcher to capture both highly focused and interdisciplinary research, guaranteeing a comprehensive review. The researcher also included general web searchers to find important grey literature.

The selected study was limited to students’ learning outcomes (performance, achievement, attitude, motivation, interest, and retention of practical knowledge skills) in STEM, which brought the number of articles to 18, the duration was restricted to

13 years from 2012 to 2024 .see fig 1.this cut down the numbers of article to 15. Therefore, any study before 2012 is excluded. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were set to ensure that the selected studies were relevant and appropriate for answering the questions. Table 1 presents the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this study.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

S/N	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
1	Full text article.	Incomplete article.
2	Any studies conducted from 2012 to 2024.	Studies conducted before 2012.
3	Manuscripts written in English.	Any other language other than English.
4	Reference journals.	Non reference journals, articles, books, thesis.
5	Studies on field performance, achievement, motivation, retention, interest or attitude in biology.	Studies do not include field trip and any other variables from inclusion criteria.

After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total number of 15 articles were found to be suitable for inclusion in this review. The articles were analyzed and discussed in accordance with the research questions. The framework of the results from the review was tabulated using 11 items/elements and used as data for analysis and discussion of findings. The items are the serial number, Author, Year. Title, Type of Publication, Location, Educational level, Methodology, STEM field, equity and access focus, learning outcomes and key findings. To obtain authentic and qualitative data on the effects of virtual field trips and other instructional strategies on learning outcomes, only complete and full-text articles published in peer-reviewed journals were selected and reviewed. Most of the journals were reputable. Therefore, the findings of these studies are expected to have high accuracy and precision.

Results

Tables 1, 2, 3, and 4 present the distribution of research on the effect of virtual field trips on STEM education by country, type of publication, STEM field, and educational level, respectively.

Table 1: Frequency of Studies by Country

Country	Frequency	Studies
Afghanistan	1	[9]
Asia	3	[7][8][13]
Indonesia	2	[10][11]
Europe	1	[14]
Malaysia	1	[3]
Nigeria	3	[1][5][12]
Netherlands'	1	[6]
Turkey	1	[4]
Thailand	1	[2]
USA	1	[15]

Table 1 shows the distribution of the studies by country. From the review, it can be observed that the Asian continent has the highest number of studies, followed by Nigeria, which has three (3) studies.

Table 2: Frequency of the Studies by type of Publication

Type of publication	Type of publication
Journal	14
Conference	1

Table 2 shows the distribution of studies by type of publication. Of the 15 articles reviewed, 14 studies were journals, only one is conferences.

Table 3: Frequency of the Studies by STEM field

STEM field	Frequency	Studies
Biology	5	1,3,5,6,11
Chemistry	3	2,12,14
Physics	2	4,10
Engineering	3	8,13,15
Mathematics	1	7

Table 3 indicated a total of five STEM fields where the empirical studies was carried out. The STEM field with the highest record is Biology, followed by chemistry and

engineering with 3-3 each, physics 2 and mathematics 1 respectively.

Table 4: Frequency of the Studies by Educational Level

Educational level	Frequency	Studies
University	9	1,2,4,5,6,13,14,15
Secondary school	4	3,9,10,12
Primary school	2	7,11

Of the fifteen (15) articles reviewed, 9 studies were conducted with university students, 4, involved secondary school students as participant, only 2, research was conducted with primary school students.

Table 5: Frequency of the Studies by Research Design

Research Design	Frequency	Studies
Quasi-experimental	11	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,12,14
Experimental	4	10,11,13,15
Action research	1	15

Findings in Table 5 presents three (3) research designs were utilized by the researchers. They include quasi experimental, experimental, and action research design. The frequency shows greater adaptation of quasi experimental research design than experimental design.

Table 6: Frequency of the Instruments used by the Researchers

Instrument for data collection	Frequency	Studies
Test	13	2,3,4,6,7,8,11,12,13,14
Questionnaire	3	1,5,9
Expert validation sheet	1	10
Quiz	1	15

Table 6 provides the details of the instruments used in data collection by previous researchers. The instrument used three (3): questionnaire, test, and quiz. Tests have the highest frequency of 11,

questionnaire (3), and quiz with one each (1), respectively.

Table 7: Learning Outcomes Measured and virtual field trips in STEM field

Learning Outcomes Measured	Frequency	Studies
Achievement	5	2,3,7,11,12
Attitude	1	4
Interest	7	8,9,10,12,13,14,15
Performance	3	1,5,6
Practical skills	2	8,14
Motivation	5	1,2,4,6,10
Retention	0	0

The common learning outcomes examined by researchers on the effect of virtual field trips in learning STEM include interest (7), achievement and motivation with (5) each, performance (3), practical skills (2), Attitude (1), Retention with none.

Discussion

The findings of this systematic review are discussed based on the research question. The research question, what is the distribution of research on the effect of virtual field trips in the SEM field by country, type of STEM publication field, and educational level. The results revealed that of the 15 articles that investigated the effect of virtual field trips on secondary school students' learning outcomes predominantly originated from the Asian continent, followed by Nigeria, with the record of three studies. This is because, Asian countries are leaders in educational technology, with their governments and institutions heavily investing in new ways of teaching. Nigeria's presence with three studies is notable because it shows the country's proactive approach to using technology to overcome educational challenges. Researchers in Nigeria are likely exploring virtual field trips as a cost-effective way to give more students access to quality STEM learning, especially in a country with a large, diverse population.

The finding that almost all the studies were published in academic journal can be as a result Journals are considered the primary and more prestigious outlet for publishing finalized, in-depth, and rigorous research. Regarding the subject matter, biology emerged as the most frequently studied STEM field with five articles, followed by chemistry and engineering with three studies each, physics with two studies, and mathematics one. The dominance of biology in the reviewed studies on virtual field trips in STEM is likely because the subject is a natural fit for this technology. Biology heavily involves concepts that are best understood through observation of living systems and diverse ecosystems, which are often impractical, expensive, or impossible to visit in person. Virtual field trips provide a perfect solution by allowing students to explore environments like rainforests, coral reefs, or the human body in a safe and accessible way.

In contrast, Engineering and Chemistry often require a more hands-on, experimental, and practical learning approach that is more challenging to fully replicate with current virtual field trip technology. While virtual tools can be used to simulate labs or show a construction site, they cannot fully replace the tactile experience of manipulating equipment, building prototypes, or conducting chemical reactions. This practical and tangible nature of engineering and chemistry might explain why these fields have a lower frequency of research on virtual field trips compared to the visually and observation-driven nature of biology. Interestingly, despite the focus on secondary school learning outcomes, most of the reviewed articles were conducted at the university level, with only four conducted at the secondary school level, while two studies were conducted in primary schools. This can be as a result of student's developmental stage and the complexity of technology.

Additionally, the curriculum at these levels is more specialized, often requiring access to specific, and sometimes dangerous or distant, environments (e.g., a chemical lab, a geological dig site, or a distant ecosystem) that are perfect for a virtual experience.

Research question two ask about the distribution of research design and instrument used by the researchers in assessing the effect of virtual field trips on students' learning outcomes in STEM education and found that the researchers predominantly employed quasi-experimental designs (11 out of 15), while three (3) studies utilized true experimental designs and only one study employed action research. This preference for quasi-experimental designs suggests a practical adaptation to real-world educational settings with full randomization of participants. However, the primary instruments used by the researchers for data collection were tests and questionnaires, with only one study that used quizzes. This shows a clear preference for direct assessment of knowledge and student opinions, focusing on measurable results.

The research question three (3) asks the learning outcomes examined by the researchers in assessing the effect of virtual field trips in STEM field; The result of the findings revealed that student interest emerged as a frequently examined learning outcome in virtual field trip research, with several studies specifically measuring this aspect (Albina, 2017; Sari et al, 2019; Monita & Ikhsan, 2020; Saniyyati et al, 2021; Dongyang et al, 2023; Faula et al, 2023; Hope et al 2024). This focus reflects the belief that these trips are effective at motivating students and improving their learning outcomes. While Norbaizura & Khamisah, 2015; Sita et al., 2020; Chattavut, 2021; Emrah &Recep, 2023; & Hope et al., 2024 specifically measured student achievement in virtual field trips, other studies like Sari et al., 2019; Jiyang et al., 2020; Chattabut, 2021;

Emrah & Recep; & Lawal, 2023) reported an increase in students' motivation when exposed to virtual field trips. While Sari et al. (2019) and Dongyang et al. (2023) examined practical skill development; they found that virtual field trips were effective in this area. This shows that researchers are looking for broader impacts beyond test score. Interestingly, none of the studies in this review specifically investigated the impact of field trips on knowledge retention. However, concentration of studies on university-level education limits the generalizability of findings to younger learners, who may interact differently with VFTs. Additionally, the predominance of studies from Asia suggests the need for more culturally diverse research to understand the global applicability of VFTs in STEM education.

Research question four asks about the key findings of the effect of virtual field trips on students' learning outcomes in STEM. This question was answered using Tables 2 and 8. The review consistently demonstrates that the integration of virtual field trips (VFTs) in STEM education positively affects various student learning outcomes. The results also show that virtual field trips not only spark students' interest in STEM, but also lead to improved achievement, motivation, practical knowledge skills, and attitude. Furthermore, a critical benefit of VFTs, as identified in this review, is their potential to offer valuable opportunities for students from underrepresented groups and minority backgrounds. These virtual experiences can effectively mitigate geographical and socioeconomic barriers and provide access to rich and diverse STEM learning environments that might otherwise be inaccessible. This inclusivity is particularly significant for promoting equitable access to quality STEM education and fostering a broader participation in diverse student populations. Overall, the findings underscore VFTs as a powerful and

inclusive pedagogical tool in STEM education that is capable of enhancing multiple learning outcomes while addressing systemic access disparities.

Conclusion

This systematic review confirms the positive impact of VFTs on STEM education, particularly in enhancing student interest, achievement, performance, attitudes, practical skills and access among underrepresented groups. By providing a comprehensive analysis of recent studies, this paper contributes to a deeper understanding of VFTs' role in promoting equity and access in STEM education. Future research should prioritize conducting studies in primary and secondary school settings to determine the effectiveness of field trips for younger students. Also, research should prioritize examining the impact of virtual field trips on knowledge retention.

References

- Akçayır, M., Akçayır, G., Pektaş, H. M., & Ocak, M. A. (2016). Augmented reality in science laboratories: The effects of augmented reality on university students' laboratory skills and attitudes toward science laboratories. *computer in human behaviour*, 57.
- Anila, D. and Boone, J. (2021). Effects of VR on students learnin: A scoping review. *E dMedia+ innovate learning, Online, United states*.
- Boris, B. N. (2017). Effect of virtual analytical chemistry laboratory on enhancing students' research skills and practices; research in learning technology.
- Dongyang, A., Hui, D., Ccheng S., Yiwen, Xx., Lin, Z., Yichuan, D. (2023). Evaluation of virtual reality application in construction teaching; a comparative study of undergraduates. *journal of applied sciences*, vol 10, p 6170.
- Emrah. A., & Recep, C. (2023). Effect of educational virtual reality game on primary school students achievement and engagement in mathematics. *Interactive learning environment*, 32 (3), 1467-1484.
- Foley, K. (2010). *A big focket guide to using and creating virtual field trips*. kirkaland: tramline: 5th edition.
- Hope, A.N., Anari, M.I., Agube, C.C., Udonkang, W. (2024). Effect of virtual field trip instructional strategy on student achievement and interest in chemistry in akwa ibom state, Nigeria, . *global journal of educational research*, vol.23 (4).
- Jiayan Z.P. Peter L. Julia C. Pejman S. Jan O. Wallgrün¶ A.K. (2020). Learning in the field: comparison of desktop, immersive virtual reality, and actual field trips for place-based stem education, . *IEEE conference on virtual reality and 3d users inte*.
- Khotimah, S.H. Krisnawati, N.M. & Budi, A.S. (2021). contribution of virtual field trip and spatial intelligence towards improvement inscience in science learning achievement og elementary school student. *4th internatioal conference on mathematics and science education*.
- Lawal, A. (2017). *Impact of laboratory technique enriched with safety training on academic performance and attitude towards practical biology among N.C.E students in Katsinastate Nigeria*. An unpublished master's Thesis. Department of Science Education, ABU Zaria,
- Lawal, A.B, Idris, M., Yusuf A. Muhd, A. (2023). Comparative analysis of virtual and outdoor laboratory strategies on academic performance of NCE biology students in katsina and kano states, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovation Scientific Research a Review*, Vol. 05, Issue, 05, pp.4510-4515.
- Monita F A and J Ikhsan. (2020). Development Virtual Reality IPA (VR-IPA) learning media for science learning, *Journal of physics; conference series*.
- Mahya, B. (2017). Cognitive Knowledge, Attitude toward Science, And Skill Development In Virtual Science laboratory.
- Norbaizura, H., Kamisah O. (2015). Effectiveness of a virtual field trip (vft) module in learning biology. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education-TOJDE J.*, Volume: 16 Number: 3 Article 8.

- Opalewski, K.G. & Leary, O.L. (2019). Defining interactive virtual learning in mesium educatio: a shared perspective. *journal of mesium education*, 44, (3), 229-241.
- Paula, F.G., Zhongxin, X., Jannil, A., Uwe, R., Britta, S., (2023). Virtual field trips for conveying hydrological engineering content; *education and information technology*, 26 (6), 6977-7003.
- Raheem, K. A. (2024). A systematic review of the effects of virtual field trips on secondary school students cognitive proficiency in biology. *SSRN eLibrary*, 57.
- Salman, A. (2023). Virtual Field trips and their effect on student learning: a comparison of knowledge assessment for physical versus virtual field trips in a construction management course; . (2) 290-302.
- Saniyyati, C.N., Razall, N., Othman, H., Aini, N.A., (2021;). The acceptance and interest of students in using virtual reality for learning mathematics, . *universal journal of educational research*, 9(12), 1949-1961.
- Sari, U., Barun, C., Busayin, M. P. (2019). The effects of virtual and computer based real laboratory applications on the attitude, motivation and graphic skills of university students; *international journal of innovation in science and mathematics education*,, 27 (1). 1-17.
- Sita H. K., Nofi M. K., Abusiri and Agus, S.B., (2021). Contribution of Virtual Field Trip and Spatial Intelligence toward the Improvement in Science Learning Achievement of Elementary School Student's. *Conference Proceedings 2320*. Published Online.
- Sharafadeen, S.A, and Adekunle, I. O. (2024). Exploring the impact of virtual field trips on secondary school students cognitive competence in biology; a systematic review. *Semanticsscholar.org*
- Tafa, T.O., Olanrewaju, F. I., & Adamu, B. (2020). Effects of the use of ict as innovative teaching tools on academic achievement of science education students. *west African journal of science and educational research*, pp, 62-70.
- Uğur Saria, H. Miraç P, Harun C, Talip K. (2019). Effects of virtual and computer based real laboratory applications on the attitude, motivation and graphic skills of university students. . *international journal of innovation in science and mathematics edu*, 27(11)1-
- Anila, D. and Boone, J. (2021). Effects of VR on students learnin: A scoping review. *E dMedia+ innovate learning, Online, United states*.
- Foley, K. (2010). *A big focket guide to using and creating virtual field trips*. kirkaland: tramline: 5th edition.
- Khotimah, S.H. Krisnawati, N.M. & Budi, A.S. (2021). contribution of virtual field trip and spatial intelligence towards improvement inscience in science learning achievement og elementary school student. *4th internatioal conference on mathematics and science education*.
- Mahya, B. (2017). Cognitive Knowledge, Attitude toward Science, And Skill Development In Virtual Science laboratory.
- Opalewski, K.G. & Leary, O.L. (2019). Defining interactive virtual learning in mesium educatio: a shared perspective. *journal of mesium education*, 44, (3), 229-241.
- Raheem, K. A. (2024). A systematic review of the effects of virtual field trips on secondary school students cognitive proficiency in biology. *SSRN eLibrary*, 57.
- Sharafadeen, S.A, and Adekunle, I. O. (2024). Exploring the impact of virtual field trips on secondary school students cognitive competence in biology; a systematic review. *Semanticsscholar.org* 20(5).
- Zanetis, J. (2010). The Beginners Guide to Interactive Virtual Field Trips. Learning and Leading with Technology. 37 (6), 20-23.